

A THREE DIMENSIONAL DAMAGE MODEL FOR UD COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A three dimensional constitutive model for the prediction of intralaminar failure in unidirectional (UD) continuous fibre reinforced polymers is proposed. The constitutive model relies on physically based failure criteria and the prediction of the orientation of potential fracture planes. Damage evolution is modelled by degradation at these fracture planes.

Keywords: UD composites, continuum damage mechanics, failure criteria

INTRODUCTION

The intralaminar failure mechanisms of UD composites are complex. Depending on the loading, failure modes like fibre rupture, fibre kinking and inter fibre failure (IFF) can be observed. Research of the past decades has identified that UD composites tend to fail along certain fracture planes. As a result, a realistic numerical representation of the failure mechanism requires modelling of damage initiation and propagation on these fracture planes. The constitutive model proposed here relies on the prediction of such fracture planes specific to each failure mode. Subsequent damage evolution on these planes is modelled using energy principles thus resulting in a correct representation of UD failure mechanisms.

PREDICTION OF THE ONSET OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION

The developed constitutive model relies on the prediction of the onset of damage evolution by the use of physically based three dimensional failure criteria. The model considers three independent modes of damage: 1 fibre rupture (Hashin criterion [1]), 2 fibre kinking (a combination of Pinho model [2] and Puck criterion [3]) and 3 IFF (Puck criterion [3]). All above mentioned failure criteria enable the calculation of a damage mode specific parameter e_i , called the material exposure, which enables an assessment of the likelihood of the onset of damage. Damage will initiate when the following condition is satisfied

$$e_i \geq 1 \text{ for } i = 1 \text{ or } 2 \text{ or } 3. \quad (1)$$

The material exposure is calculated from the following failure criteria

Fibre rupture (only for $\sigma_{11} \geq 0$)

$$e_1 = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_f}\right)^2} & \text{for } \sigma_{11} \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Fibre kinking (only for $\sigma_{11} < 0$)

$$e_2 = \begin{cases} \sqrt{(1-p_t)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_n^{kink}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}^{kink}}{R_{n1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}^{kink}}{R_{nt}}\right)^2} + p_t \frac{\sigma_n^{kink}}{Y_t} & \text{for } \sigma_n \geq 0 \\ \sqrt{(p_c)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_n^{kink}}{Y_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}^{kink}}{R_{n1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}^{kink}}{R_{nt}}\right)^2} + p_c \frac{\sigma_n^{kink}}{Y_c} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

IFF

$$e_3 = \begin{cases} \sqrt{(1-p_t)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}^{iff}}{R_{n1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}^{iff}}{R_{nt}}\right)^2} + p_t \frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_t} & \text{for } \sigma_n \geq 0 \\ \sqrt{(p_c)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}^{iff}}{R_{n1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}^{iff}}{R_{nt}}\right)^2} + p_c \frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_c} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The above failure criteria are homogenous in their stress terms, which results in a linear relation between the load and the material exposure e_i . The parameters X_t , Y_t , Y_c , S_f denote the commonly used UD strength properties. All other parameters are specific to the respective failure theory and described in detail elsewhere [2, 4].

The stress based failure criteria detect the onset of damage by assessing the normal stress and the two shear stresses which are acting on the plane where damage will initiate. For fibre rupture, this plane is aligned with the material coordinate system and is known to form perpendicular to the fibre direction. IFF and kinking often occur in planes that are not aligned with the material directions. Therefore, the above failure criteria are written in terms of fracture plane stresses σ^{kink} (kinking) and σ^{iff} (IFF). The three dimensional theory proposed by Pinho et al. [2] for the prediction of fibre kinking, is used here. The corresponding definition of the kink initiation plane is displayed in Figure 1.

Inter Fibre Failure (IFF) is predicted using three dimensional failure theory proposed by Puck [3]. The definition of the fracture plane for IFF is displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Kink initiation plane definition (after [2])

Figure 2 Definition of the IFF fracture plane (after [3])

Using fracture plane stresses for the prediction of the onset of damage evolution requires the orientation of these planes to be known. Theoretical models for the prediction of such planes have been proposed in [2, 3]. Additionally, numerically efficient algorithms for finding such planes were developed by the authors [5, 6].

MODELLING DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN UD COMPOSITES

Damage is represented using the framework of continuum damage mechanics (CDM). Unlike in many CDM models, energy dissipation is not enforced by a damage evolution function. The propagation of damage is entirely driven by the rate at which certain failure criteria are exceeded. The failure criteria introduced in the previous section are used as energy dissipation potentials, however, the respective damage variables and consequent stress reduction are obtained implicitly rather than by direct differentiation of the damage potential. The material exposure, e , is used as a non-dimensional measure of unsustainable strain energy in the RVE. The growth of damage within the RVE is represented by reducing the materials strength and stiffness. This is reflected in the model by reducing the strength in the respective failure criteria which are defined on

the damage mode specific fracture plane. The consequent stiffness degradation is modelled by returning the fracture plane stress state back on the damaged failure surface (as defined by the failure criteria) by the use of stress return algorithms. The approach is similar to the stress return to the yield surface as commonly used in plasticity models. This ensures a physically based material degradation. Furthermore, a finite element size dependent parameter is introduced into the constitutive equations in order to relate the energy dissipation to the area of the evolving fracture within the element thus reducing the mesh dependency of the solution that is characteristic for many CDM models.

Damage evolution is defined by dissipation potentials. These potentials are functions of those stress terms that contribute to damage evolution as defined in the failure criteria presented earlier. The damage evolution and consequent energy dissipation are not controlled by the underlying damage function but are given entirely by the rate at which respective failure criteria are exceeded. A damage growth function g_i is defined for each damage mode. The rate of damage growth, \dot{g}_i , is evaluated using the material exposure e_i . In the explicit FE framework the increment of damage growth Δg_i is given by

$$\Delta g_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } e_i \leq 1 \\ e_i & \text{if } e_i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Because the chosen failure criteria have show a linear relation between σ and e_i , Δg_i can be interpreted as a measure of unsustainable strain energy in the material. It should be noted that above expression is only valid for homogeneous failure criteria. The damage growth function g_i is incrementally updated by

$$g_i^t = g_i^{t-\Delta t} + \Delta g_i. \quad (6)$$

The two equations above result in damage which can only increase in value. This is a sufficient condition to fulfil the second law of thermodynamics.

Each damage mode is represented by a single scalar damage threshold variable r_i . The variable r_i is not an actual damage variable in the classical sense. It is an internal variable which controls the domain in which the material behaves elastically and can be compared to the damage threshold as used in the models as proposed by Matzenmiller [7], Curiel-Sosa [8], Boehm [9] and Maimi [10]. The threshold variable, r_i , is used to reduce the strength of the material thus resulting in reduced failure strength criteria (i.e. the elastic region of the material shrinks as damage increases). The elastic domain threshold variable is given by

$$r_i = g_i f^e. \quad (7)$$

The coefficient f^e controls the energy release of the RVE. The coefficient f^e is a function of the damage mode specific fracture energy and the size of the finite element. It is derived from a numerical calibration procedure as described in [6]. As a result, the well known mesh sensitivity of CDM is reduced. For illustration, the evolution of r for fibre rupture under uniaxial tension is displayed in Figure 3.

The elastic domain threshold is introduced into the failure criteria thus forming dissipation potentials for damage propagation. The following dissipation potentials are proposed

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Fibre rupture} \\
 e_1 = & \begin{cases} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t(1-r_1)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_f(1-r_1)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_f(1-r_1)}\right)^2} & \text{for } \sigma_{11} \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Fibre kinking} \\
 e_2 = & \begin{cases} \frac{|\sigma_{12}^p|}{S_{kink}(1-r_2)} & \text{for } \sigma_{11} < 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{IFF} \\
 e_3 = & \begin{cases} \sqrt{(1-p_t)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_t(1-r_3)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}^{iff}}{R_{n1}(1-r_3)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}^{iff}}{R_{nt}(1-r_3)}\right)^2} + p_t \frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_t(1-r_3)} & \text{for } \sigma_n \geq 0 \\ \sqrt{(p_c)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}^{iff}}{R_{n1}(1-r_3)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}^{iff}}{R_{nt}(1-r_3)}\right)^2} + p_c \frac{\sigma_n^{iff}}{Y_c} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

It should be noted that only normal tensile and shear strength parameters are reduced in response to damage growth. This takes into the account the fact that cracks can close and carry load under compressive stress.

From Equation (9) it can be seen that the damage potential for fibre kinking has not been derived from the criterion for the prediction of the onset of kinking. The reason is that kink propagation follows a different mechanism than kink initiation. Kink bands are initiated by a matrix failure around misaligned fibres. However, as kinking propagates, the failure mechanism is dominated by the rotation of misaligned fibres which finally results in visible kink bands. Therefore, a kink propagation plane is defined as shown in Figure 4. It is assumed that kinking in that plane is mainly driven by the acting in-plane shear stress σ_{12}^p . The underlying mechanisms of fibre kinking are not yet fully understood, but the simplified dissipation potential presented in Equation (9) offers a good approximation. The kink band inclination angle β (see Figure 4) depends mainly on the matrix material. Values between 10° and 30° have been reported in literature. The kink band inclination angle β has to be provided as model input. The parameter S_{kink} in Equation (9) is the shear stress σ_{12}^p at the onset of kinking.

Figure 3 Evolution of r_1 for uniaxial tension

Attempting to load the material beyond the elastic limit results in inadmissible stress states. As a consequence, the material degrades (e.g. reduction in stiffness and strength) and this is represented by the increase in damage. The proposed numerical constitutive model represents the onset and evolution of damage using the material exposure, e_i , which defines the respective internal threshold variables r_i , predicted in the linear elastic initial iteration. As a result, the current inadmissible stress state needs to be returned to the damaged failure surface in order to represent the corresponding material degradation. The concept is similar to the 'radial return' method of plasticity [11]. The implemented return algorithms for each failure mode, within the presented constitutive model, however, rely entirely on reserve factors calculated from the material exposure e_i by

$$f_i^{res} = \frac{1}{e_i}. \quad (11)$$

The reserve factor is the linear scaling factor by which the stresses of the respective failure criterion need to be multiplied in order to satisfy the condition for damage initiation/propagation (see Eqn. (1)).

Following the return algorithms for tensile and compressive damage modes are introduced. Tensile and compressive damage modes are distinguished using the stress acting perpendicularly to the predicted fracture plane.

Since the dissipation potentials are homogeneous with respect to their stress terms it is possible to calculate the corresponding reserve factors which can be used to scale the stress vector on the respective fracture planes. All three stresses which are acting on the fracture plane need to be damaged in tension. However, not all stress terms used in the definition of the failure surface contribute to damage propagation in the compressive regime. The normal compressive stress actually impedes damage propagation. Consequently, a different approach is needed for each damage mode which takes into account the respective damage mechanism.

Figure 4 Definition of kink band propagation plane

Fibre kinking is driven by the shear deformation as fibres rotate, and leads to the fibre breakage. Therefore, the in-plane shear stress σ_{12}^p and the normal stress σ_{11}^p are degraded. For IFF under compression, the normal stress is not degraded as cracks are able to transfer normal compressive load. Only the shear stresses on the fracture plane are affected by the damage mechanism.

The stress return algorithms for the tensile and compressive damage mode are summarised in Table 1. Figure 5 visualises the stress return strategies.

Table 1 Stress return for the damage modes

Damage mode	Reserve factor	Stress return
Fibre rupture (tension)	$f_1^{res} = \frac{1}{e_1}$	$\sigma_{11} = f_1^{res} \sigma_{11}$ $\sigma_{12} = f_1^{res} \sigma_{12}$ $\sigma_{13} = f_1^{res} \sigma_{13}$
Fibre kinking (compression)	$f_2^{res} = \frac{1}{e_2}$	$\sigma_{11}^p = f_2^{res} \sigma_{11}^p$ $\sigma_{12}^p = f_2^{res} \sigma_{12}^p$
IFF (tension)	$f_3^{res} = \frac{1}{e_3}$	$\sigma_n^{iff} = f_3^{res} \sigma_n^{iff}$ $\tau_{n1}^{iff} = f_3^{res} \tau_{n1}^{iff}$ $\tau_{nt}^{iff} = f_3^{res} \tau_{nt}^{iff}$
IFF (compression)	$f_3^{res} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - 2p_c \frac{\sigma_n}{Y_c}}{\left(\frac{\tau_{n1}}{R_{n1}(1-r_3)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}}{R_{nt}(1-r_3)}\right)^2}}$	$\sigma_n^{iff} = \sigma_n^{iff}$ $\tau_{n1}^{iff} = f_3^{res} \tau_{n1}^{iff}$ $\tau_{nt}^{iff} = f_3^{res} \tau_{nt}^{iff}$

Damaging the stress terms on the actual fracture planes provides a realistic representation of UD failure mechanism. For the purpose of demonstration, the constitutive model has been implemented into the commercial explicit FE solver LS-DYNA.

Figure 5 Stress return (2D schematic)

The formation of a matrix crack under transverse compression, and the propagation of a kink band under uniaxial compression in fibre direction have been modelled. A UD ply is loaded in-plane transverse to the fibres (see Figure 6 (a)). The initiation and formation of a matrix crack was successfully modelled. The result of a uniaxial compression simulation where the load is applied in fibre direction is displayed in Figure 6 (b). A kink band was initiated and propagated at the predefined propagation angle β .

Figure 6 Modelling of the propagation a matrix crack (a) and a kink band (b) in a UD material

APPLICATION TO THREE POINT BENDING

A number of three point beam impact bending experiments have been performed under quasi-static and impact loading regimes. These experiments have been modelled in order to demonstrate the capability of the model to correctly predict the experimentally observed damage mechanisms. The experiments were performed with beams (100mm x 9mm x 3mm) made from a cross ply laminate of carbon/epoxy.

A number of beams were tested at a span of 30mm which finally resulted mainly in interlaminar failure (delamination). However, the initial damage originated, due to fibre kinking, in the ply near the surface indented by the impactor. Subsequently, damage propagated by IFF and fibre kinking forming an inclined kink-band. Finally, a delamination initiated and formed the final failure mode. No damage was observed in the region directly underneath the impactor, which is assumed to be suppressed by the compressive through thickness stress. The model correctly predicted the location of the onset of damage in the surface ply. Damage progressed, in a similar manner to that observed experimentally, through the underlying plies and causing further fibre kinking and IFF. Finally, the IFF model predicted the direction of the matrix crack, which eventually resulted in modelling delamination using the IFF criterion. The large-scale delamination observed in the experiment could not be modelled in its entirety because the present implementation has numerical stability problems. This continues to be investigated. The sequence of initiation and propagation of damage mechanisms in the large portion of the analysis, however, were predicted correctly.

Figure 7 Comparison of model prediction and experimentally observed damage for a span of 30mm

The experiments performed with a span of 50mm showed tensile failure on the back face of the specimen. Fibre rupture and IFF occurred simultaneously. Subsequently, large scale delaminations formed. The model correctly predicted the onset of damage by fibre rupture and IFF. Subsequently, the damage did not propagate through the entire thickness of the specimen as often observed in damage models. The IFF model predicted a fracture angle of 90° and damage continued to grow along one ply thus forming a delamination. Again, the full extent of delamination could not be predicted due to numerical stability reasons.

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Figure 8 Comparison of model prediction and experimentally observed damage for a span of 50mm

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